

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MICALLEF****FIRST NAME: CRISTINA****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA 401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2019 on Windows 10)

ACHIEVING EXCELLENCE IN ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The resource provides clear instructions on what is expected from Euclid's doctorate students to achieve excellence in academic writing. The level of detail that the toolkit presents helps me to develop a clearer picture of what is expected from the student. Being a public health physician and now reading for a doctorate in International Public Health requires precision and an eye for detail, which are essential skills in my profession.

2) PERIOD ONE (1) COURSEPACK

The resource provided for this period is divided into several sections, presenting different essential guidelines in academic writing. I will take a few points which I feel are the most important and go through them in further detail.

The First Section, which deals with *Essay Writing the Basics* presents in a simplified manner, the seven basic points which are a prerequisite for essay writing (EUCLID 2015, 2-5). One of the points which struck me is the section highlighting the importance of dedicating adequate time to re-read the draft to include new ideas, make sure that it is easy to follow, and carry out any amendments before submitting the final version to the tutor. This guideline inevitably encourages me to start writing the document early to achieve these objectives.

Euclid University stresses the gravity of plagiarism, in which I am in full agreement, as this is a severe offense in both academic writing and in drafting public health documents. Acknowledging the work of other authors demonstrates respect towards their work while identifying the source of information gives credibility to the work presented by students.

Another essential aspect that struck me is that the students are to achieve a logical flow in their coursework. The ideas being brought forward in a project must be presented in a flowing manner, that is, one point leading to the next. A flowing presentation enables the reader to understand better the topic being discussed and proves that the author is well structured in his/her work. This section, which is the second section of the coursepack, is presented in a PowerPoint style.

The section *Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Paper* presents ten rules of thumb. The second point advises the students to keep focused on the topic being discussed and point four stresses the importance of presenting the study in a well-defined way and in a manner that is easily understood by the reader. It also points out that discussions in academic writing are to be taken seriously. The suggestion to read out aloud the draft before submission is a good piece of advice to help improve the quality of the document being written. This section addresses plagiarism again, emphasizing that Euclid University takes this issue very seriously. This section offers suggestions as well for alternative use of the English language, and in my opinion, this presents an opportunity for improving the level of writing and professionalism (EUCLID 2015, 43-45).

Another section that transported me back to basics in proper course writing was the section LIT-101 Review. The main point which caught my attention was the use of commas, and I must admit that sometimes I do struggle with identifying where to insert or not to insert commas in paragraphs (EUCLID 2015, 46)! The points in this section served me as a useful revision for specific grammatical issues, such as how fractions and numbers are presented.

I really appreciated the *Latin Abbreviations and Expressions* section as even though I regularly make use of them, I was not so familiar with some of them.

Some of the points seemed obvious at this level of education, but I instantly felt that it took me back to my medical student days, during which, we were drilled on how to present clinical cases and medical records. These guidelines shall assist the drafting of the thesis project, which I shall present, and make it more understandable to the reader who can be either a colleague or someone who is new to the topic, or who is neither a public health specialist nor a medical doctor.

3) THE CHALLENGING STYLE

The Turabian Style, or also known as the Chicago Manual Style, which is named after Kate Turabian (EUCLID 2015, 66), is the standard style requested by Euclid University. The student is introduced to this style in the coursepack provided as part of

period 1. Through standardization and level of perfection, the student is expected to achieve a level of excellence. I must admit that I am not acquainted with this style, as during my previous studies and during my professional career as a public health physician, I was trained in using the American Psychological Association (APA) method. It is challenging for me to switch from the APA style to the Turabian style but I am confident that I will master it whilst preparing the different papers to be presented during my doctorate. Two main differences between the two styles, which caught my eye are that:

- The Turabian Style makes use of both in-text citations and footnotes whereas the APA style only allows the former and,
- The Reference List in the Turabian style requests that the entire first and middle name are spelled out fully whereas in the APA style, initials can be used for each author.

Zotero is a software that facilitates the process of implementing the Turabian Style with regards to citations and bibliography. This is one of the many different styles which can be chosen from the readily available academic writing styles within the tool itself. It also helps the student to keep a record of the books, articles, and documents (both searched online and offline) that have been collected during the Ph.D. program so that they can be accessed easily. I am not at all familiar with Zotero and am looking forward for this new opportunity to learn this referencing software.

4) CONCLUSION

During my practice as a public health physician and as a trainee, I have prepared various documents, including the master's thesis. The materials that I have worked on to date were addressed to different audiences, such as fellow doctors, politicians, and the general public, including persons with learning disabilities. This experience helps me to understand better the point highlighted in the coursepack. Therefore, it makes much sense (Euclid 2015, 44) that the information presented in the thesis should be kept simple and presented in a structured manner, so that it can be easily understood by others. As the US Navy noted in 1960, *Keep it Simple, Stupid* (KISS Principle 2020).

This coursepack served me as an excellent refresher in preparing myself for the upcoming study periods and the thesis project. The new material which I was introduced to during this period, will surely help me to become a better academic writer. It also helps me to be in a better position to relay the message, which I hope will be of benefit and interest to other readers and to make a difference in the lives of the most vulnerable.

REFERENCES

Euclid University. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Retrieved from:
<https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/CUEsEiHd7B/ACA-401%20Coursepack.pdf>
(accessed on 20th February 2020)

KISS Principle. 2020. In *Wikipedia*.
https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=KISS_principle&oldid=940277545
(accessed on 20th February 2020)

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.